

Complicated Oscillations in the Problem of the Competition of Species

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Some families of mathematical models of biological populations competing for common food are considered. Dynamic properties of these models are investigated on an assumption that one or several populations are strongly prolific, which means that the corresponding malthusian coefficients are rather large. On the basis of a special asymptotic method a problem of behavior of the initial system solutions can be reduced to a significantly simpler problem of dynamics of the finite-dimensional mappings. In particular, it has been shown that irregular relaxation vibrations are typical for the solutions of these mappings and, as a result, for the solution of the initial equation systems. It is interesting to note that these vibrations are of large amplitudes.

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1. Introduction

Extensive literature [1–8] is devoted to the study of mathematical models of interacting populations. In Ref. [1] a universal approach to the construction of mathematical models of multi-species communities has been developed. These models are based on the logistic equation with a delay, which describes well the dynamics of the change of an isolated population inhabiting uniform environment. In this paper we investigate dynamical properties of the models under the assumption that at least one of the populations has high fecundity, i. e., the corresponding Malthusian coefficients are sufficiently large. On the basis of the special asymptotic method [8], the problem of the behavior of the solutions of the initial systems can be reduced to the constructed substantially simpler problem of the dynamics of the finite-dimensional mappings. In particular, it is shown that for the solutions of these mapping,

i. e., of the initial systems of equations, irregular relaxation oscillations are characteristic. It is interesting to note that the amplitudes of these oscillations are rather large. The content of the paper is based on Ref. [8].

In the work [1] a system of equations describing the dynamics of population size change (N_{j1} (preys) and N_{j2} (predators)) of the form

$$\dot{N}_{j1} = r_{j1} \left[1 + \sum_{\substack{i=1 \\ i \neq j}}^n a_{ji}(1 - N_{i1}) + \sum_{i=1}^m b_{ji}(1 - N_{i2}) - N_{j1}(t - h_{j1}) \right] N_{j1}, \quad (1)$$

$$\dot{N}_{s2} = r_{s2} \left[\sum_{i=1}^n c_{si} N_{i1} + \sum_{\substack{p=1 \\ p \neq s}}^m d_{sp} \cdot \left(\sum_{i=1}^n N_{i1} - N_{p2} \right) - N_{s2}(t - h_{s2}) \right] N_{s2}, \quad (2)$$

where $j = 1, \dots, n$, has been proposed as a model of interacting populations.

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The problem of the competition of $n \geq 2$ species inhabiting a uniform environment and competing for the same food can be modeled by the system of equations (1) with $N_{j2} \equiv 0$, $b_{ji} = 0$, i. e.,

$$\dot{N}_j = r_j \left[1 + \sum_{\substack{i=1 \\ i \neq j}}^n a_{ji}(1 - N_i) - N_j(t - h_j) \right] N_j, \\ j = 1, \dots, n. \quad (3)$$

We consider the question of the structure of the steady-state regimes of this system under an assumption that m ($1 \leq m \leq n$) species have high fecundity, i. e., that their Malthusian coefficients are sufficiently large. Under this condition the steady-state regimes in certain sufficiently general problems that are also of most interest from a biological point of view are investigated. We note that in real problems the Malthusian coefficients are not too large. However, for the steady-state regimes the asymptotic formulas constructed for the case when the Malthusian coefficients $r_j \rightarrow \infty$ can give good approximations for relatively small values of r_j too. In addition, the problem posed is also of interest because in “extreme” situations it enables us to understand more clearly the role of the various biological laws lying at the foundation of the system (1), (2), and the role of the coefficients of this system, and hence to answer the question of the applicability of the system (1), (2) itself for describing ecological problems.

2. Method of asymptotic integration

The technique by means of which the results are obtained is based on application of special procedures developed for asymptotic integration of the system (1), (2) (see Ref. [8]). Its essence is as follows. Using considerations of a biological character, in the space of the initial conditions of the original system a certain (sufficiently broad) set S is distinguished and solutions with

initial conditions from this set are considered. We succeed in constructing uniform asymptotic approximations for all such solutions and in showing that after a certain interval of time these solutions again fall into S . A succession operator, which (using the solutions) places functions from S in correspondence with a function that is also from S , is thereby defined in a natural manner. It turns out that the properties of this succession operator are determined, as a rule, by a certain mapping (of a certain region into itself). From the steady-state regimes of such a mapping we draw conclusions about the steady-state regimes of the original system. Such a scheme is described in detail in papers – see Refs. [8–13], and therefore, below, we shall not dwell on proving the results obtained. We note further that the method of asymptotic integration makes it possible to obtain uniform asymptotic formulas for the steady-state regimes with an arbitrary degree of accuracy. These formulas, however, are too cumbersome, and therefore we shall confine ourselves just to describing the approximate behavior of the solutions. We draw attention to one of the results obtained below. The steady-state regimes of the systems under consideration have a Hutchinson structure (rapid growth of a population size is succeeded by a yet more rapid fall and a long period of restoration of the average population size), except that all the fundamental parameters of these regimes execute, as a rule, complicated and irregular oscillations.

The problem of the competition of two species one of which has high fecundity is considered in Ref. [14]. Let $n = 2$ and

$$r_1 \gg 1, \quad (4)$$

i. e., the “first” species has high fecundity. For all sufficiently large values of t every solution of (3) with positive initial conditions satisfies the

inequalities

$$0 < N_j(t) < A_j \exp(r_j^0 h_j); \quad A_j = 1 + \sum_{\substack{i=1 \\ i \neq j}}^n a_{ji},$$

$$r_j^0 = r_j A_j, \tag{5}$$

and, therefore, below we shall consider only those solutions whose initial conditions satisfy these inequalities.

3. Results

We shall formulate the basic results. We suppose first that

$$a_{12} \cdot a_{21} > 1, \tag{6}$$

i. e., that one species exerts strong pressure on the other. Under this condition the equilibrium state is unstable. In Ref. [1] it was conjectured that in the case under consideration one of the species certainly dies out (as for the ordinary equations with $h_1 = h_2 = 0$). The condition (4) makes it possible to formulate the following conclusion: the second coordinate $N_2(t)$ in all solutions with biologically meaningful initial conditions tends to zero as $t \rightarrow \infty$. Mathematically, this means that in the space of the initial conditions of (3) ($n = 2$) the region from which solutions emerge into a stable steady-state regime with a nonzero second coordinate is small (and of higher order of smallness as $r_1 \rightarrow \infty$). As a result, the conditions (4) and (6) the species with the lower fecundity dies out. We note that for $h_1 = h_2 = 0$ such a conclusion does not hold.

The case when

$$a_{12} \cdot a_{21} < 1 \tag{7}$$

is substantially more complicated and more interesting. The type of attractor in the system is largely determined by the sign of the quantity $r_2^0 h_2 - \pi/2$. Suppose first that $r_2^0 h_2 - \pi/2 < 0$. It can then be stated that under the condition (4) and for all sufficiently sufficiently large r_1

the system has an exponentially orbitally stable, slowly oscillating periodic solution $(N_{10}(t, r_1), N_{20}(t, r_1))$. We shall describe its structure. Suppose for definiteness that $N_{10}(0, r_1) = 1$, $N_1(0, r_1) > 0$. We denote by $t_1(r_1)$ and $t_2(r_1)$ the first and second positive zeros of the function $N_{10}(t, r_1) - 1$, and by $T(r_1)$ the period of this function. It is found that, for $r_1 \rightarrow \infty$,

$$T(r_1) = t_2(r_1) = \frac{1}{r_1} \exp[r_1^0 h_1] \cdot \varphi(a_{12})(1 + o(1));$$

$$t_1(r_1) = h_1 + o(1); \quad \varphi(a) = e^{-1} + \int_0^1 e^{-\xi} \xi^a d\xi.$$

For each fixed $\delta \in (0, \frac{1}{2}h_1)$, uniformly in $t \in [\delta, h_1 - \delta]$, we have

$$N_{10}(t, r_1) = \exp(r_1^0 t) \cdot (1 + o(1)), \quad N_{20}(t, r_1) = o(1),$$

and for $h_1 + \delta \leq t \leq t_2(r_1) - \delta$ we have $N_{10}(t, r_1) = o(1)$. On the segment $[\delta, T(r_1)]$ the function $N_{20}(t, r_1)$ is asymptotically close to zero during a time interval of length

$$\frac{a_{21} \cdot \varphi(a_{12})}{r_1(1 + a_{21})} \exp[r_1^0 h_1] (1 + o(1)),$$

and, on an interval of length

$$[r_1(1 + a_{21})]^{-1} \varphi(a_{12}) \exp[r_1^0 \times h_1(1 + o(1))]$$

ending at the point $T(r_1)$, this function is asymptotically close to $1 + a_{21}$. We note also that

$$\max_t N_{10}(t, r_1) = (1 + a_{12}) \exp \left[r_1^0 h_1 - 2 - \frac{1}{1 + a_{12}} \right] \times (1 + o(1));$$

$$\min_t N_{10}(t, r_1) = \exp [-\varphi(a_{12}) \exp(r_1^0 h_1)(1 + o(1))];$$

$$\max_t N_{20}(t, r_1) = 1 + a_{21} + o(1),$$

$$\min_t N_{20}(t, r_1) = \exp \left[-\frac{r_2^0 a_{21}}{r_1^0(1 + a_{21})} \exp(r_1^0 h_1) \times (1 + o(1)) \right].$$

It is interesting to track the influence of the second (background) species on the character of the oscillations of $N_1(t)$. For $N_2 \equiv 0$ and $N_2 =$

$N_{20}(t, r_1)$ the oscillations are structurally similar: they have a clearly pronounced Hutchinson character. The difference is as follows. First, in the presence of a competing species the minimum of the population size N_1 is substantially greater, meaning that the oscillations become more dangerous. Secondly, the time interval during which the population size N_1 is smaller than its average value decreases. From this we can conclude that a less fecund (or more resourceful) competing species has a stabilizing effect.

Now suppose that $r_2^0 h_2 - \pi/2 > 0$. For $N_1 = 0$, in the Hutchinson equation for N_2 there is a stable periodic (non-constant) regime $N_0(t)$ of period T_0 . We shall assume that all solutions with sufficiently small (positive) initial conditions enter the region of attraction of $N_0(t)$. (When $0 < r_2 h_2 - \pi/2$ is sufficiently small or sufficiently large this assumption is evidently fulfilled.) We shall describe first the behavior of the steady-state regimes in the system (3), and then draw conclusions about the structure of the attractor in the phase space of this system. We begin by describing $N_1(t)$. Suppose that for a certain $t = \tau \in [0, T_0]$ the conditions $N_1(\tau) = 1$, $\dot{N}_1(\tau) > 0$ are fulfilled. For every $t \in (\tau, h_1 + \tau)$ we have $N_1(t) = \exp[r_1^0(t-\tau) \cdot (1+o(1))]$, and for every $t > \tau + h_1$ the equality $N_1(t) = o(1)$ is true. The latter equality is fulfilled uniformly for $t \in [h_1 + \tau + \delta, \tau + t_2(r_1, \tau) - \delta]$, where $\delta > 0$ is arbitrary and $t_2(r_1, \tau)$ is the second positive zero of the function $N_1(t) - 1$ on the interval (τ, ∞) . The situation is then approximately repeated, the role of τ being played by $t_2(r_1, \tau)$ ($t_2(r_1, \tau) = O((1/r_1) \exp(r_1^0 h_1))$). We shall describe the changes of $N_2(t)$. For $t > \tau$ this function decreases sharply to asymptotically small values and remains small for a time interval $O((1/r_1) \cdot \exp(r_1^0 h_1))$ before growing exponentially with exponent r_2^0 . The function N_2 then tends to $N_0(t + c)$. The value of the parameter c is determined, basically, by the parameters τ and r_1 . Then, for an asymptotically large time interval (of order $(1/r_1) \cdot \exp(r_1^0 h_1)$), N_2 is close to $N_0(t + c)$. Next, the situation approximately repeats itself, with the role of τ again being played by $t_2(r_1, \tau)$.

We set

$$\bar{\tau} = t_2(r_1, \tau) \bmod T_0 \quad (\bar{\tau} \in [0, T_0]). \quad (8)$$

As it turns out, the mapping (8) of the segment $[0, T_0]$ into itself determines the structure of the attractors in the phase space of the system (3). The right-hand side of (8) is such that every segment of length d_0/r_1 ($d_0 > 0$ is fixed) is mapped into the whole segment $[0, T_0]$. From this, in particular, we can draw the conclusion that when the Hutchinson structure of the oscillations is preserved all the parameters of the steady-state regimes change in a rather random manner, and therefore the oscillations in the case under consideration have an irregular character.

We shall consider the problem of the competition of two highly fecund species. We shall assume that in (3) the parameters r_1 and r_2 are rather large, i. e.,

$$r_1 = \lambda \rho_1 \frac{1}{1 + a_{12}}, \quad r_2 = \lambda \rho_2 \frac{1}{1 + a_{21}}, \quad \lambda \gg 1. \quad (9)$$

In the case when the population size of one species is zero, the other species undergoes intense oscillations, and for an asymptotically large time interval its population size is close to zero. In view of this, it is natural to consider those solutions of (3) whose coordinates on a certain sufficiently large time interval are close to zero. We shall describe here the steady-state regimes to which (as $t \rightarrow \infty$) all solutions possessing the above-mentioned property tend. (It is evident that this system does not have other stable regimes.)

In the case of harsh competition, when $a_{12} \cdot a_{21} > 1$, one of the species certainly dies out.

Let $a_{12} \cdot a_{21} < 1$, i. e., the two species coexist. Their oscillations are Hutchinson-like in structure, and have a complicated and irregular character. We shall describe the steady-state regimes that arise in this problem.

In the course of an asymptotically large (as $\lambda \rightarrow \infty$) time interval the values of N_1 and N_2 are sufficiently small, and grow exponentially, with exponents $\lambda \rho_1$ and $\lambda \rho_2$, with increase of t . For definiteness we shall assume that at $t = 0$ the

conditions $N_1(0) = 1$, $\dot{N}_1(0) > 0$, $N_{20}(0) = \xi < 1$ are fulfilled. We set

$$\Delta_1 = \exp \left[\frac{\rho_2(1 - a_{12}a_{21})}{\rho_1(1 + a_{21})} \exp(\lambda\rho_1 h_1) \right];$$

$$\Delta_2 = \exp \left[\frac{\rho_1(1 - a_{12}a_{21})}{\rho_2(1 + a_{21})} \exp(\lambda\rho_2 h_2) \right].$$

We denote by $\kappa_1 = \kappa_1(\xi)$ a non-negative number such that $\Delta_1^{\kappa_1} \cdot \xi \leq 1$, $\Delta_1^{\kappa_1+1} \cdot \xi > 1$. The number κ_1 for the solutions of (3) has a transparent meaning: the function $N_1(t)$ completes (for $t \geq 0$) exactly $\kappa_1 + 1$ spikes before the function $N_2(t)$ completes a spike.

We denote by t_1^j, t_2^j, \dots ($j = 1, 2$) the positive zeros of the function $N_j(t) - 1$. Then, on the segment $[0, t_1^2 - \delta]$, the behavior of the function $N_1(t)$ is approximately the same as for the Hutchinson equation. For the function $N_2(t)$, for $t \in [0, t_1^2 - \delta]$, intervals of exponential growth (with exponent $\lambda\rho_2$) alternate with brief intervals of decrease (each of duration $\approx h_1$). For example, for $0 < t \leq 2h_1$,

$$N_2(t) = \xi \exp \left[\lambda\rho_2 t - \frac{\lambda a_{21}}{1 + a_{21}} \int_0^t \exp \left[\lambda\rho_1 \tau - \frac{1}{1 + a_{12}} \exp \left(\lambda\rho_1 (\tau - h_1) \right) \right] \left(1 + o(1) \right) d\tau \right].$$

We note also that at $t = t_{2i}^1$ ($N_1(t_{2i}^1) = 1$) we have $N_2(t_{2i}^1) = \Delta_1^i \xi$ ($0 \leq i \leq \kappa_1$), and at the point $t = t_1^2$ ($N_2(t_1^2) = 1$) we have $N_1(t_1^2) = \eta = (\Delta_1^{\kappa_1+1} \cdot \xi)^{-\frac{\rho_1}{\rho_2}} < 1$. We then denote by $\kappa_2 = \kappa_2(\xi)$ a non-negative integer such that $\Delta_2^{\kappa_2} \cdot \eta \leq 1$ and $\Delta_2^{\kappa_2+1} \cdot \eta > 1$. The description of the behavior of the solutions is then repeated, with the index 1 replaced by 2 and with ξ replaced by η . Thus,

$$N_1(t_{2(\kappa_1+1)}^1) = 1, \quad \dot{N}_1(t_{2(\kappa_1+1)}^1) > 0,$$

$$N_2(t_{2(\kappa_1+1)}^1) = \bar{\xi},$$

where

$$\bar{\xi} = \Delta_2^{\frac{\rho_2(\kappa_2(\xi)+1)}{\rho_1}} \cdot \Delta_1^{\kappa_1(\xi)+1} \cdot \xi \cdot (1 + o(1)). \quad (10)$$

The mapping (10) of the segment $[0, 1]$ into itself determines the structure of the steady-state

regimes of the system (3) (and their stability). It is clear that this mapping is rather complicated, and therefore its attractors (and hence those of (3) too) have a complicated structure. Thus, in the case under consideration irregular oscillations are characteristic. In this problem it is interesting to note the following: the spikes in the population sizes of the competing species turn out to be strongly separated in time.

We consider the system (3) for $n > 2$. We assume that the Malthusian coefficients of the first m ($1 \leq m \leq n$) species are sufficiently large, i. e., $r_j^0 = \lambda\rho_j$, $\lambda \gg 1$, for $j = 1, \dots, m$. For $m = 1$ this problem represents the direct generalization of the problem of competition of two species one of which has high fecundity. On the qualitative level all the conclusions remain the same. The main difficulty is connected entirely with the construction of a stable stationary regime of the system of $n - 1$ equations to which the original system reduces when $N_1 \equiv 0$.

For $m = n$ the problem is investigated fully. It generalizes the problem of the competition of two highly fecund species. Here we confirm the conclusion that the spikes in the population sizes of the species (if they coexist) are separated in time. Just as was done in the problem of the competition of two highly fecund species, here we succeed in constructing an n -dimensional mapping (of a certain region into itself) that determines the structure (and stability) of the stationary regimes of the system (3).

In the case $1 < m < n$ the conclusions of the two cases developed above are combined. The dynamics of the change of the group of variables with labels from 1 to m is described in the same way as in the problem of the competition of two highly fecund species, while the dynamics of the change of the variables with the other labels is described as in the problem of the competition of two species one of which is highly fecund. We note that the steady-state regimes in the cases under consideration here are fundamentally more complicated than for $n = 2$, inasmuch as the mapping determining their structure is essentially multi-dimensional.

4. Conclusion

In the problems described here it is possible to obtain coefficient criteria that guarantee the survival or dying out of certain species. The path to be followed to do this is based on the construction of asymptotic formulas for the solutions of the original system.

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